

FABRICATION OF SOLAR POWERED RIVER WATERCLEANING MACHINE

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Abstract:

The project focuses on fabrication of the solar powered river water cleaning machine. The “Solar Powered River Water Cleaning Machine” is a machine which is removing the floating waste debris from water surface and collecting for safely disposes of it. The rivers which are dumped with huge amount of sewage and loaded with pollutants, toxic materials, debris etc. Due to increasing in water pollution in the form of waste debris, it is hazarding the life of aquatic animals and makes their life in danger. A machine will lift the floating waste debris from the water bodies, this will ultimately results in reduction of water pollution and lastly the aquatic animal’s death to these problems will reduce. The solar will helps for charge the battery and improve the battery span. The main aim of the project to reduce the man power, time consumption for cleaning the river, in this project we have store the energy in the battery and used this energy for river cleaning with the help of a motor and chain drive arrangement.

Key words: Motor, chain drive, Propeller , Conveyor, River, Wastage, Garbage, Pollution

1.INTRODUCTION

The "Solar Powered River Water Cleaning Mahine" is employed when there is waste debris in the water body that has to be removed. This equipment comprises of a waterwheel-driven conveyer system that collects and removes waste, rubbish, and plastic waste from bodies of water. This also reduces the problems we have when collecting waste. A machine will remove waste surface material from water pollution, reducing the number of aquatic animals that die as a result of these difficulties. It comprises of a belt-driven system that pulls trash from the water. The purpose of this project will be to clear surface water debris from rivers, ponds, lakes, and other bodies of water.

The word "waste water" refers to the flow of used water from residences, commercial operations, enterprises, and institutions into a treatment facility via a properly designed network of pipes. The

most serious consequence is respiratory ailments caused by the chemical wastes that are cleansed, making it a difficult issue for township authorities to address. Even with technology, appropriate industrial sewage disposal and sewage cleansing remain difficult tasks in today's society. Drainage pipes are employed for this purpose, and sadly, human life might be lost when removing obstructions in drainage systems.

2. OBJECTIVES

Pollution Mitigation: The primary goal is to minimise river pollution by removing impurities such as plastics, chemicals, organic waste, and other detritus. This helps to improve water quality and protect the ecology.

Environmental Protection: It is essential to safeguard the ecosystem by keeping contaminants out of the river system. The device seeks to mitigate the effects of human activity on aquatic environments and life.

Public Health Improvement: Because fewer waterborne illnesses are possible, cleaner water improves public health. Eliminating impurities from river water guarantees clean supplies of drinking water and lessens the health risks related to contaminated water.

Preservation of Biodiversity: Rivers support diverse ecosystems. Cleaning the water helps in preserving aquatic biodiversity by maintaining suitable habitats for various species of fish, plants, and other organisms.

3. LITERATURE REVIEW

Prof. N.G. Jogi et al: mentioned that one of the most contaminated rivers in India is the Ganges.

Toxins and almost 29 crore litres of sewage are discharged into the Ganges. To gather trash from the lake, they have proposed using a pedal-operated boat that has a conveyor attached to it. This conveyor makes it feasible to gather trash such as straws, paper bags, plastic bottles, food wrappers, beverage cans, and marine debris. This methodology does not require fuel.

Mr. P. M. Sirsat et al: stated that a machine is made to clean the surface of rivers in accordance with river cleaning programmes like "Namami Gange," "Narmada Bachao," and several major and medium-sized projects in different cities like Ahmadabad, Varanasi, etc. This device is made up of DC motors, an RF transmitter and receiver, a propeller, PVC pipes, a chain drive, and a conveyor that is connected to the machine to collect waste from bodies of water. Additionally, it has a collecting plate that is connected to chain drives and a conveyor belt that are turned by a PMDC motor.

4. MATERIALS & METHODOLOGY

The basic step is to fabrication of base frame of the project by using hand cutting machine and electric welding machine to withstand the model and its operation. The base frame is made of square channel.

1. The hollow pipe is put together at the base frame using a nut and bolt and an L-section. PVC pipe is used in its construction, and fastening is used. This pipe's function is to float on water by supporting the weight of the project while compressed air is added to create a differential pressure head that makes the machine float on the water.
2. L- Section is welded in base frame which is used to hold the hollow pipe with the help of nut and bolt.
3. T section is welded on base frame to support the bearing and shaft.
4. T- Section is assembled on base frame by welding. It is used to support the pulley with the help of bearing and shaft.
5. The torque is transferred from the motor to the chain drive via a conveyor belt. In the machine, two shafts are assembled. With the use of an inclined selection and a T-section, shaft 1 is installed at the machine's front chain drive, while shaft 2 is put at the rear chain drive.
6. One plate of 200*150 mm is welded at T section from 170 mm from base for mount motor for driving pulley of belt drive
7. The drive source of our project is an electric motor having 12V and 7.6 ampere current which is used to drive gear train, for collecting mechanism.
8. Gear is welded on pulley shaft and another gear is weld on motor shaft drive used to transmit the power from motor to conveyor belt pulley.
9. Drive is required to carry a load as desirable to complete the project objective.
10. One method of moving mechanical power from one location to another is by chain drive. It is frequently used to transfer power to propellers, especially on motorcycles and bicycles. In addition to cars, a broad range of other machinery also employ it. A roller chain, referred to as the drive chain, transfers the power by passing over a sprocket gear, its teeth meshing with the holes in the chain links. When the gear is turned, the chain is pulled, applying mechanical force.

5.CONSTRUCTIONANDWORKINGMECHANISM

5.1. Construction:

The construction and working principle of a river water cleaning machine can vary based on its design and specific functionality. However, here's a generalized overview of the construction and working.

1. By enabling independent wheel movement, the double wishbone suspension system reduces force transfer between the sides. The control arms pivot to maintain camber angle and wheel alignment while the spring and damper system absorbs vertical movement when the vehicle encounters bumps. Hull: To enable it to traverse the river, the machine usually has a buoyant hull or platform that floats on the water's surface. Typically, the hull is composed of sturdy, buoyant materials like aluminium, fibreglass, or plastic.
2. **Frame and Chassis:** A sturdy frame or chassis provides structural support to the machine and houses various components. It may be made of steel or aluminum for strength and durability.
3. **Power Source:** The machine can be powered by an electric motor, internal combustion engine, or renewable energy sources like hydrokinetic turbines or solar panels, depending on how it is designed..
4. **Pumps and Suction Mechanism:** Pumps or suction mechanisms are used to draw water and debris into the machine for cleaning. These may include centrifugal pumps, diaphragm pumps, or vacuum systems.

WORKING PRINCIPLE:

1. **Navigation:** The machine is deployed into the river and navigates along predefined routes or areas of concern where pollution needs to be addressed.
2. **Water Intake:** Pumps or suction mechanisms draw water from the river surface into the machine, along with floating debris, trash, and pollutants.
3. **Filtration:** The water passes through a filtration system where debris and pollutants are captured and separated from the water. This may involve the use of mesh screens, filters, or other separation mechanisms.
4. **Storage:** Debris and pollutants collected by the filtration system are stored in onboard collection bins or tanks for later disposal or recycling.
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6.COMPONENTS

- DC MOTOR
- PVC PIPES
- SOLAR PANEL
- COLLECTING TANK

6.1 DC MOTOR:

A DC motor operates on the basis of the interaction of electric currents and magnetic fields, which produces rotational motion. This is an explanation of how it functions:

A DC motor is a type of electrical motor that generates mechanical force by means of direct current (DC). The most popular kinds rely on magnetic forces generated by coil currents. Almost every kind of DC motor has an internal mechanism, either electrical or mechanical, that allows it to occasionally reverse the direction of the current flowing through a portion of the motor.

SPECIFICATIONS:

Operating voltage (V):12
Rated speed (RPM):200
Rated Torque(kg-cm):1.5
Load Current (A):0.3

PVC PIPES:

River water purification machines that use PVC pipes are a useful and affordable option. PVC pipes are appropriate for a range of water-related applications because they are corrosion-resistant, lightweight, and strong. This is an example of how a river water cleaning machine can use PVC pipes.

Water Intake:An intake system to collect water from the river can be made with PVC pipes. A pump could be part of this setup to circulate water inside the device.

Filtration System:Filters of many kinds, including mesh screens, sand filters, activated carbon filters, and even specialised membranes for ultrafiltration, can be placed within PVC pipes. These pipes serve as the filtration system's structural support, directing water flow through several filtration stages to get rid of pollutants, debris, and silt.

These are two hollow pipes joint together by permanent fastening with the help of M-seal.

Water Intake

Specification: Length=1220mm

D1=2000cm

D2=180cm

6.2 SOLAR PANEL:

Power Generation: River water cleaning equipment can be powered by solar panels, which have several advantages. However, in order to maximise system performance and dependability, parameters like solar irradiance, shading, panel orientation, and energy storage capacity must be taken into account. The long-term sustainability and efficacy of the solar-powered water cleaning device also depend on correct installation, upkeep, and monitoring.

Energy Storage: The water cleaning machine can run in low- or no-light conditions, as at night or in overcast weather, by using solar panels to charge batteries or other energy storage devices throughout the day. The system's stability and uninterrupted functioning are guaranteed by energy storage.

6.3 COLLECTING TANK:

A collecting tank is an essential part of a river water cleaning equipment that collects and holds the cleaned water until it is released or dispersed. This is the usual operation of the collecting tank in such a system.

Receiving Treated Water: The treated river water is sent into the collecting tank after it has gone through a number of cleaning procedures, including filtration, disinfection, and maybe chemical treatment. This tank serves as a temporary storage space for the cleaned water.

Storage Capacity: The volume of water to be treated, the river's flow rate, and the intended use of the cleaned water can all affect the collecting tank's capacity. While smaller tanks could be adequate for applications requiring lower flow or intermittent operation, larger tanks are necessary for systems handling large amounts of water or running continuously.

All things considered, the collecting tank is essential to the functioning of a river water purification system since it offers a means of short-term storage for the cleaned water and makes it easier for it to be distributed for different uses without compromising system effectiveness or water quality.

6.4 FABRICATION IMAGE

6.5 RESULT AND CONCLUSION

The design and fabrication of “Solar Powered River water Cleaning Machine” project is based on research and literature from many journals and papers that are pertinently available. It is constructed in a way that allows for operational flexibility. This idea is simple, affordable, and has a lot of potential for further cost savings. The "Solar Powered River water Cleaning Machine" project was created with the intention of being highly cost-effective and beneficial for cleaning rivers and ponds.

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